

Maxwell's Laws and Lorentz Force from Special Relativity, Lorentz Gauge and Gauss' Law?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 5, 2024

Classical electromagnetism is often expressed in terms of the four Maxwell EM equations and the Lorentz force. Here we speculate that these equations follow from the assumption of Gauss' law (keeping its form as seen in the moving frame) and special relativity, together with the Lorentz gauge.

Gauss' Law

Gauss' law is stated as:

$$\text{Grad dot } E = \text{charge density } \epsilon_0 \quad ((1))$$

We argue that this is a pivotal equation because it introduces the notion of a gradient of force. In Newtonian mechanics, one usually deals with $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$ for a conservative potential, but $\text{grad dot } F$ does not appear frequently. The notion of $-\text{grad } \phi$ is also used in classical electromagnetism with $F = q E = -q \text{ grad } \phi$ for a source charge at rest. "q" is a test charge.

We note that for a spherical charge distribution about the origin, one expects, by symmetry that E is radial, i.e. $E(r) e(r)$ where $e(r)$ is the unit vector along the r vector. If one multiplies the scalar value of $E(r)$ by the area of a sphere, this is mathematically equivalent to:

$$\text{Integral grad dot } E \text{ dvolume} \quad ((2))$$

It is known that E is proportional to the source charge. The question which arises is whether different spherical distributions of this charge yield different $E(r)$ values. We suggest that given the volume integral in ((2)), one may create a volume integral for each spherical charge density. There is no notion of any moments of charge for a spherical distribution.

Gauss' law is equivalent to the statement that for $E(r) e(r)$, one cannot distinguish between different spherical charge distributions. Thus, this seems to be an information statement. All spherical charge distributions yield the same $E(r) e(r)$ for r outside of the charge distribution.

A key feature of ((1)) is that it involves the grad of E which itself may be written as:

$$qE = -\text{grad } \phi \quad ((3)) \quad \text{according to Newtonian mechanics.}$$

Special Relativity and Lorentz Gauge

((1)) is a single Maxwell EM equation, holding only for a charge at rest at this point, with $F=q E$.

In order to proceed further, we argue that one may make use of special relativity. Consider a charge Q at rest interacting with a test charge q , also at rest some distance away. The potential energy is:

$$\text{Potential energy} = q \phi \quad ((4))$$

((4)) should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector, yielding:

$$(0, q \phi) \rightarrow (q A_c, q \phi') \quad \text{where } \phi' = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \phi \quad \text{and } q A_c = -q v \phi / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((5))$$

For the results seen in the moving frame, one should rewrite x, t of the rest frame in terms of x', t' of the moving frame.

The question we ask is: What happens to Gauss' law? The integral of the charge density is still Q which is an invariant, even though the charge density should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector so that $(0, \text{charge density}) \rightarrow (j, \text{charge density})$.

Gauss' law holds even if one does not have a symmetric charge distribution, i.e. E is not a function of r . As a result, one may have a skewed electric field in the moving frame, but integrating $\text{grad dot } E$ over all volume should still yield the invariant charge Q .

A question which arises is: Does $E = -\text{grad } \phi$? We argue that as seen from a frame moving with constant $-v$, there is now $q / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \phi$ and $A = -v\phi / \sqrt{1-vv}$. If $-\text{grad } \phi$ represents an E field type force in the moving frame, then derivatives of A should do the same.

For ϕ , only $\text{grad } \phi$ yields a vector which uses a linear change, i.e. grad .

For A , which is a vector, both d/dt partial and grad may be used, but the outcome should be a vector. This suggests force pieces, using the vector v (velocity as well) of:

(We use ϕ now to represent the potential as seen in the moving frame, i.e. drop all $'$ values.)

$$dA/dt \text{ partial}, \quad v (\text{grad dot } A) \quad \text{and} \quad v \times (\text{grad } \times A) \quad ((6))$$

One might argue that one may include $v \text{ d}\phi'/\text{d}t \text{ partial}$ as well.

Thus, one could have an overall force of:

$$F = q\{-\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial} + v \times (\text{grad } \times A) + v (\text{grad dot } A + 1/c \text{ d}\phi/\text{d}t)\} \quad ((7a))$$

Let us assume for the moment that: $\text{grad dot } A + 1/c \text{ d}\phi/\text{d}t \text{ partial} = 0$ ((7b)). (This is called a Lorentz gauge and we may see later whether this assumption is warranted or not.)

((7)) with the Lorentz gauge represents the new overall force, i.e. the Lorentz force, but which pieces correspond to E (electric field) and which do not?

$\nabla \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ allows for forces inward, radial type forces which lead to radial type energy, (like $\epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ in the rest frame). Given that Q is unchanged in the moving frame, it would be good to have $-\text{grad} \phi$ as well as terms which integrated to 0 in $\int \text{grad} \cdot \text{force} \, d\text{volume}$.

$-\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial is a symmetry breaking force because it points in the direction of v and immediately yields 0 for a surface area integral, dotted to the normal of the surface area. Thus, we suggest:

$$E = -\text{grad} \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial} \quad ((8))$$

Thus $\text{grad} \times A$ must be some kind of new force (called the magnetic force.)

At this point, one has the Lorentz force and Gauss' law $\text{grad} \cdot E = \text{density} \, \epsilon_0$, which in a sense is imposed because one is left with an extra force piece $qv \times B$. $\text{Grad} \cdot E = \text{density} \, \epsilon_0$, has the same form as in the rest frame except that now: $E = -\text{grad} \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial}$.

How does one obtain the other three Maxwell EM equations?

One may immediately see that: $\text{grad} \cdot B = 0$ because:

$D_j (e_{klm} \, dl \, A_m)$ is symmetric in jl for $djdl$, but antisymmetric in kl for e_{klm} , hence it is 0.

Next, $\text{grad} \times E = -\frac{dB}{dt} \text{ partial}$ because:

$-\text{Grad} \times \text{grad} \phi - \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \text{ grad} \times A = -\frac{dB}{dt}$ given that:

$\text{Grad} \times \text{grad} \phi = e_{ijk} (dj \, dk) \phi = 0$ because $dj \, dk$ is symmetric in jk , while e_{ijk} is antisymmetric.

Only one Maxwell EM equation is left, which involves current density. We argue that Gauss' law is key because it involves:

$$\text{Grad} \cdot E = -\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi - \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \text{ grad} \cdot A = \epsilon_0 \text{ charge density} \quad ((9))$$

ϕ and charge density are fourth components of 4-vectors. Thus, it would be good to have a Lorentz invariant operator acting on ϕ . $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad}$ is a piece, but $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}$ (partial is missing) in order to have a Lorentz invariant D'Alembertian. Furthermore, $\frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \text{ grad} \cdot A$ is a problem.

Given that ((9)) represents the fourth component of a 4-vector, one needs a similar equation for the other three components, In this case, one wants a D'Alembertian with A , u_0 current density and one must deal with: $\frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \text{ grad} \cdot A$. Furthermore, $\frac{dE}{dt} \text{ partial}$ should be similar to a current density and should be present. This term yields:

$$dE/dt \text{ partial} = -\text{grad } d\phi/dt - d/dt d/dt \text{ partial } A \quad ((10a))$$

((10a)) is good because it supplies $d/dt d/dt A \text{ partial}$ needed for a D'Alembertian (Lorentz invariant). $-\text{grad } d\phi/dt \text{ partial}$ is a problem and $\text{grad dot grad } A$ is missing.

Given that $dE/dt \text{ partial}$ and $u_0 j$ are vectors, one may obtain $\text{grad dot grad } A$ from:

$$\text{Grad } x B = \text{grad } x (\text{grad } x A) = \epsilon_{ijk} d_j \epsilon_{klm} d_l A_m = d_j d_i A_j - d_j d_j A_i \quad ((10b))$$

$-\text{grad } d\phi/dt \text{ partial}$ from ((10a)) and $\text{grad } (\text{grad dot } A)$ from ((10b)) disappear due to the Lorentz gauge which we suggested in ((7b)) i.e. $d/dt \phi (1/c) + \text{grad dot } A=0$.

This gauge is also useful because:

$$-d/dt \text{ partial grad dot } A = d/dt d/dt \phi \text{ partial}$$

which is needed in ((9)) to create a D'Alembertian and remove $d/dt \text{ grad dot } A$.

Thus, as shown above:

$$dE/dt \text{ partial} + u_0 j = 1/u_0 \text{ grad } x B \quad ((11))$$

One now has four Maxwell EM equations and the Lorentz force form as well as:

$$D'Alembertian \phi = \epsilon_0 \text{ charge density} \quad \text{and} \quad D'Alembertian A = u_0 j \quad ((12))$$

((12)) are consistent with Lorentz transformations.

As a result, using Gauss' law, special relativity and the Lorentz gauge, one obtains Maxwell's EM equations and the Lorentz force.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Gauss' law is the pivotal equation in obtaining Maxwell's EM equations and the Lorentz force equation. If one uses special relativity and introduces the Lorentz gauge, one may obtain the four Maxwell EM equations and the Lorentz force equation. The key it seems is to preserve the form: $\text{grad dot } E = \epsilon_0 \text{ charge density}$ which means that E is no longer $-\text{grad } \phi$, but $-\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial}$. Another possible force $\text{grad } X A$ cannot be added to E because it does not preserve Gauss' law and so it is called a different force (magnetic). The Lorentz force may be written in terms of A and ϕ only, as may the Maxwell EM equations, but one needs specific equations linked to charge and current density which are in keeping with Lorentz transformations (A, ϕ) is a 4-vector as is (current density, charge density). Charge density appears through Gauss' law, so one seeks an equation with current

density such that : $\square \phi = \epsilon_0 \text{ charge density}$ and $\square A = \mu_0 \text{ current density}$.

Gauss' law is assumed and $\text{grad dot } B$ and $\text{grad } \times E = -dB/dt \text{ partial}$ follow immediately. Gauss' law involves the fourth component of two 4-vectors, ϕ and charge density and contains grad dot grad , suggesting a Lorentz invariant \square . This occurs if the Lorentz gauge $1/c \text{ d}\phi/\text{dt partial} + \text{grad dot } A = 0$ holds. One needs a similar equation for A and $\mu_0 j$, the current density. One may use the Lorentz gauge together with $dE/dt \text{ partial}$ (which is physically like a current) and $\text{grad } \times A$. This leads to the final Maxwell EM equation: $\text{grad } \times B = \mu_0 j + dE/dt \text{ partial}$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lorenz_gauge_condition